

EELISA

European University

EELISA ENTREPRENEURSHIP ACTION PLAN

Deliverable 7.3

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This document is prepared within the work package WP7 – “Create the ‘embedding’ for EELISA-wide R & I structures (Optimize outreach)”, as deliverable D7.3 “EELISA entrepreneurship action plan” of the project EELISA INNOVation and COMmon REsearch strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA InnoCORE), co-funded by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101035811.

The EELISA entrepreneurship action plan is a concept for increasing the outreach of entrepreneurial activities across EELISA to different target groups and rests on three pillars: Firstly, an EELISA landscape of startup support that gives an overview of the key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at all EELISA partner institutions along all three different stages of the startup journey: nucleation, incubation, and acceleration; secondly, the sharing of those key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at all EELISA partner institutions along all stages of the startup journey wherever possible and meaningful; and thirdly, the implementation of an EELISA-wide startup initiative. The EELISA entrepreneurship action plan will outline these three pillars and will be implemented in the third year of the EELISA InnoCORE project.

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Glossary - Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The EELISA communities are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

EELISA Innovation Talks. EELISA Innovation Talks aim to raise the public awareness – and thus also the scientific awareness – for the knowledge generated in EELISA and are publicly visible events and fora for discussion in the real and digital world. The events shall thematise the use of technology and innovation for sustainable development and develop a strong brand of EELISA for a broader public. EELISA Innovation Talks are an event series set up by EELISA InnoCORE.

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

R & I. Research and Innovation

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 45 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of EELISA Communities: challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project,

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 General Considerations

With the “EELISA entrepreneurship action plan” (D7.3) EELISA InnoCORE develops “a concept for increasing the outreach of entrepreneurial activities across EELISA to different target groups”, as the main objective was already formulated in the Grant Agreement. More specifically, with the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan we seek to implement two different tasks: Firstly, to create an infrastructure of business incubators across EELISA (task 7.2) and secondly, to implement an EELISA-wide startup initiative (task 7.3). From these two tasks three different pillars can be distilled on which the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan is based:

1. The first pillar is an EELISA landscape of startup support. In order to create a meaningful infrastructure of business incubators across EELISA, we have to know what our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at each EELISA partner institution are in the first place. To generate this knowledge – an EELISA landscape of startup support –, we will start the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan with an overview of the key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at each EELISA partner institution along all three stages of the startup journey: nucleation, incubation, and acceleration. We will indicate which ones have already been opened to EELISA and which ones have not yet been opened, but might be of interest for future activities.

2. The second pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan will be the sharing of our respective key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses along all stages of the startup journey. The EELISA landscape of startup support developed in this deliverable can already serve as a basis for this. Further steps will be to interlink the offers that we have identified as far as meaningful and possible and to promote them via our EELISA media channels for innovation and also via EELISA Communities. In the future (possibly in WP10 of EELISA phase II), we could also transform the mapping in the first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan into an overview on the EELISA website to make our resources better visible, accessible, and coordinated. Furthermore, we will continue our discussions about connecting and sharing our key players and resources of startup support by joint events and small thematic meetings.

3. The third pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan will be the implementation of an EELISA-wide startup initiative. We will not only try to open our existing key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses along all stages of the startup journey for EELISA, but also to organize joint events, especially startup contests and mentoring programs. The aim of this initiative is not only to fill the gaps of existing offers and to create additional valuable activities, but also to open our innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems for startups from EELISA partners to raise the probability of a successful market entry of startups in all our partner cities and eventually across the entire EELISA innovation ecosystem. We will primarily aim at existing startups at the verge of market entry. For them we will organize various activities like boot camps, workshops and startup contests. All of these activities will help the startups to become familiar with general basics like “pitching” or “product market fit”, to get informed about how investors actually work in different national markets, to learn from

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each other, and to build an international network already at an early stage. Furthermore, these activities will give them access to startup ecosystems of other countries and also create opportunities for international collaboration. With our activities, we want to raise the probability of a successful market entry of startups in all our partner cities and eventually across the entire EELISA innovation ecosystem. This is particularly relevant as the EELISA consortium covers lucrative national economies and auspicious markets for startups. The highlight of our activities will be the EELISA startup contest that will be hosted in the third year of the EELISA InnoCORE project by FAU and to which the winners of local startup competitions or selected startups from all EELISA partners will be invited.

In the following, the three pillars of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan will be described in more detail: 1. The first part of the following chapter will start with the EELISA landscape of startup support. 2. The second part will explore the possibilities of meaningfully sharing our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses. 3. The third part will elaborate the outline of an EELISA-wide startup initiative that will be implemented between June 2023 and May 2024. This startup initiative will continue the entrepreneurship activities of the EELISA Unfolds project and also serve as a basis for future entrepreneurship activities in EELISA phase II.

3 The three pillars of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan

This chapter outlines the three pillars of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan. In the first part of this chapter, the EELISA landscape of startup support will be outlined by mapping the key startup support institutions, services, programs and courses at each EELISA partner institution on all three different levels of the startup journey: nucleation, incubation, and acceleration. This is crucial for getting an overview of the EELISA innovation ecosystems and more specifically to create a meaningful infrastructure of business incubators across EELISA. The mapping will include indications which key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses have already been opened to EELISA and which ones have not yet been opened, but might be of interest for future activities. In the second part of this chapter, the possibilities of sharing the key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses outlined in the first part of the chapter will be discussed. This discussion will help to better interlink and promote the offers that we have identified so that we can consequentially improve the sharing of our startup support resources. In the third part of this chapter, the implementation of an EELISA-wide startup initiative will be outlined. With this initiative we will go beyond the opening of our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses for all EELISA partners in offering new joint events that will meaningfully complement existing offers and create new opportunities for our startups and founders.

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3.1 The first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan: The EELISA landscape of startup support

The following EELISA landscape of startup support will be the first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan. It provides an overview of the key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on all three levels of the startup journey: 1. We want to conceptualize the first level as “nucleation”, because it helps to create the nucleus of a future startup. This level of nucleation is about providing basic startup skills and knowledge that allow potential founders not only to become interested in founding, but also to conceive, evaluate, and further develop their initial business idea before actually founding their startup. 2. The second level is called “incubation”. This level is about providing advanced startup skills and knowledge, but also resources to those who are willing to actually found their own startup. 3. The third level is called “acceleration”. This level is about providing professional startup skills, knowledge, and resources to founders who have already established their startup and now want to bring it to the next level. The EELISA landscape of startup support will go through these three different levels of the startup journey and each time first list the key startup support institutions and services, and then the key startup support programs and courses. Finally, we will provide a summary overview of the EELISA landscape of startup support in two figures: Figure 1 provides a summary overview of the key startup support institutions and services (“EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part A”) and figure 2 provides a summary overview of the key startup support programs and courses (“EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part B”). This will greatly help to get a better overview of the existing infrastructure of startup support at all EELISA partner institutions and to meaningfully integrate them wherever possible into the EELISA entrepreneurship ecosystem. We try to list all key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses at all EELISA partner institutions and we will indicate which ones have already been opened to EELISA and which ones have not yet been opened, but might nevertheless be of interest for future activities.

3.1.1 Key startup support institutions and services at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)

The following table provides an overview of the key startup support institutions and services at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of nucleation. From the table it can be seen that every EELISA partner institution has at least one key startup support institution or service on the level of nucleation. Some of them have already been opened to EELISA and more can be opened to EELISA in the future. But there are also many key startup support institutions and services that are not English-speaking and some that cannot be opened to EELISA (for example because they are funded by another project).

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Key startup support institutions and services on the level of nucleation at UPM

1.	Name	CAIT UPM
	Short description	<p>CAIT stands for “Centro de Apoyo a la Innovación Tecnológica” (Center for the Support of Technological Innovation). The aim of CAIT UPM is to help detecting high potential ideas, technologies and entrepreneurs, educating UPM community in innovation and entrepreneurship and creating high growth potential companies at UPM’s community. Therefore, it develops its work around four specific parameters that define the birth of the project: team building, scientific and technological knowledge, supporting resources, and business model. In order to achieve these goals, the Entrepreneurship Program offers the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advice and assistance. • Monitoring of the project from the very first step. • Analysis of the project feasibility. • Training activities targeted to the needs of the team. • Visibility for investors. • Support in seeking funding. • Business Plan Competition, actúaupm.
	Link to website	https://montegancedo.upm.es/Transferencia/CAIT
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
2.	Name	Entrepreneurship group UPM
	Short description	<p>The entrepreneurship group UPM is made up of individuals from different centers within UPM. The group is engaged in:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Community engagement 2. Idea generation 3. Business planning
	Link to website	There is no website, but there is a contact e-mail address: creacion.empresas@upm.es
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No

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	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes
3.	Name	Banco Santander (Partnership between UPM & Banco Santander)
	Short description	The partnership involves leveraging the resources and expertise of both organizations to support the creation and growth of innovative new businesses, community engagement, and collaboration on research and development.
	Link to website	https://www.metaredx.org/global/que-es-metaredx.html
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd
<i>Key startup support institutions and services on the level of nucleation at ENPC</i>		
1.	Name	Makerspace
	Short description	Ecole des Ponts' Makerspace is a place for knowledge sharing and interdisciplinary design; come make your scholar or personal projects and share your know-hows with the community!
	Link to website	https://makerspace.enpc.fr/#/
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
2.	Name	Fablab Descartes
	Short description	Fabrication laboratory with different machines for the construction of prototypes.
	Link to website	https://www.descartes-devinnov.com/fablab-descartes/

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	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
<i>Key startup support institutions and services on the level of nucleation at FAU</i>		
1.	Name	FAU Startup Service (Gründungsberatung)
	Short description	The FAU Start-up Service provides aspiring entrepreneurs and young companies with sound advice. Students, staff or professors at FAU are supported both before launching their company and whilst building their business. The Start-up Service regularly invites founders and young entrepreneurs to events covering topics relevant to starting out in business and provides information on competitions for founders and start-ups.
	Link to website	https://www.fau.eu/outreach/innovation-and-start-ups/successful-start-ups/
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
2.	Name	FAU Digital Tech Academy (DTA)
	Short description	The Digital Tech Academy is the overarching HUB for digitization and entrepreneurship at Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg. It is embedded into the university department of strategic planning S-Outreach as 'Knowledge and Technology Transfer' which is the single point of contact for Spin-off services, Joint R&D projects, IP management, continuing education and event management. The Digital Tech Academy scales and professionalizes digital entrepreneurship endeavors at FAU and integrates existing (extra-) curricular offerings and provides novel formats with charisma and leverage. In addition, the DTA frames, harmonizes, and builds a central platform for all offerings in the field of "Digital Entrepreneurship". The Digital Tech Academy secures its high-quality expectations through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a direct connection to the university administration • a board with central responsibilities • a network throughout all faculties and university institutions

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the close relationship to the start-up and innovation networks of our region through our top notch alumni network with support from the FAU spin-off services <p>The Digital Tech Academy consists of two main pillars: the Digital Tech Fellows Program and the Starting Business Ideas @FAU Program.</p>
Link to website	https://www.dta.fau.de/
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Partly
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Partly

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of nucleation at ITU

1. Name	ITU GINOVA (Center for Entrepreneurship and Innovation)
Short description	ITU GINOVA is a dedicated center for early-stage entrepreneurship at ITU. The center aims to provide nascent and early-stage entrepreneurship support for ITU stakeholders (i.e. undergraduate and graduate students, researchers and staff). The center facilitates entrepreneurship via an annual entrepreneurship program named Jumpstart. The program is composed of entrepreneurship training and mentoring. In addition, the center is involved in various EU projects on entrepreneurship and actively organizes ad hoc seminars, workshops and training courses in the entrepreneurship and innovation domains.
Link to website	https://ginova.itu.edu.tr/
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Probably yes (based on capacity planning and alignment)

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Key startup support institutions and services on the level of nucleation at SNS

1.	Name	Knowledge Transfer Office (KTO) of SNS
	Short description	<p>The research carried out at the SNS has led to technological innovations with industrial application offering new, original and concrete solutions to a technical problem. These inventions are protected by the prescriptions of prevailing laws, including patents, which give exclusive rights to their owners.</p> <p>The decision as to its possible territorial extension is taken on the basis of the prospects for development of the technology involved. Given the multidisciplinary and collaborative nature of the research carried out at the SNS, the inventions are often jointly owned among various research organizations with which the SNS has strong historical ties.</p> <p>At present there is a portfolio of around fifteen patents, mainly in the context of Life science and Industry 4.0. To see the list of titles and owners of patents of the SNS, you can consult the knowledge-share platform, or the Italian public research or JoTTO showcase.</p>
	Link to website	https://www.sns.it/en/valorisation-research
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes, in case of joint research activities
2.	Name	JoTTO office
	Short description	<p>JoTTO is the Joint Technology Transfer Office of School IMT Advanced Studies Lucca, Scuola Normale Superiore and Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna of Pisa. JoTTO was constituted on October the 1st 2015 when the three universities signed a decree for its activation. Since 1st April 2017 also the School for Advanced Studies IUSS Pavia has joined JoTTO. While the International School for Advanced Studies SISSA and Gran Sasso Science Institute GSSI of L'Aquila joined JoTTO in 2020. The goal is to provide the six schools with a common service of exploitation of research across various scientific fields and about the Third University Mission.</p> <p>JoTTO relies on the complementary technology transfer experience and scientific knowledge of the four Schools. Its goal is to identify new promotional strategies for the exploitation of</p>

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	<p>research results, by means of protection of intellectual property, development of start-up and collaboration with enterprises and corporations.</p> <p>JoTTO promotes the direct application, enhancement and use of knowledge to contribute to the social, cultural and economic development of society, by means of a common strategy involving:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • intellectual property management in international or national projects or in research agreements with other partners; • exploitation and dissemination of university research results, encouraging their use in enterprises and corporations; • strengthening the relationships with enterprises and corporations making available new technologies, knowledge, research personnel and equipment; • supporting teachers and researchers in pointing out productive and commercial implications of their inventions/discoveries, including the creation of new "spin-offs" companies. <p>It will be possible for teachers, researchers, students and companies to take advantages of JOTTO asking for advise about protection of intellectual property (patents, trademarks, design, copyright, know-how) and creation of Start Up (business idea identification, support to the accreditation process).</p>
Link to website	https://www.jointto.it/en
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
3. Name	Contamination Lab
Short description	CLab Pisa aims to promote entrepreneurial culture and innovation, valuing ideas and interdisciplinarity. It allows participants from different disciplinary fields to get to know each other and work together on common projects, developing their Soft Skills, along with planning, organizational, and communication capabilities.
Link to website	http://contaminationlab.unipi.it/en/home-english/

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	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of nucleation at SSSA

1.	Name	Start Cup Toscana 2023
	Short description	Start Cup Toscana is the business plan competition that rewards the best high-tech entrepreneurial initiatives based on the university research and offers the opportunity to turn an idea into a business, with the support of training activities and assistance in drawing up the business plan.
	Link to website	http://www.startcuptoscana.it/
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of nucleation at UPB

1.	Name	UPBiz Entrepreneurship Center
	Short description	UPBiz Entrepreneurship Center's purpose is to provide support and oversee the development and progress of student entrepreneurs while encouraging the entrepreneurial spirit among the student body. Moreover, the Center aims to consolidate UPB as an upholder of the business environment and student entrepreneurship by adding business-related workshops and events to the student program. UPBiz has three focus directions: Business Education, Mentoring, and Financing.
	Link to website	http://antreprenoriat.upb.ro/en/
	Is it English-speaking?	No

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	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Not likely in the near future
<i>Key startup support institutions and services on the level of nucleation at BME</i>		
1.	Name	BME US(3)
	Short description	BME US(3) is the incubator of the University of Technology & Economics in Budapest. Our Startup Spinoff Studio is created to foster university-based innovation and boost the entrepreneurial mindset within academia. Team US(3) works in co-operation with corporates and investors to ignite the flourishing potential at the university.
	Link to website	https://us3.bme.hu/
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
<i>Key startup support institutions and services on the level of nucleation at PSL</i>		
1.	Name	Technology Transfer Services at PSL
	Short description	<p>Since its creation in 2010, PSL has leveraged its multidisciplinary ecosystem for innovation and entrepreneurship. The university's role is to create synergies aligned with two complementary goals: stimulating entrepreneurship, and supporting technology transfer opportunities for basic and applied research.</p> <p>Entrepreneurs – whether researchers or students - find advice and support for their ventures in the dedicated structures that PSL provides. Through support from PSL technology transfer structures, researchers can select the most suitable approach for fully valorising their inventions and results.</p> <p>The core thrust of the Innovation and Entrepreneurship Department is to help researchers and students create startups through an array of opportunities, including PSL's innovation and entrepreneurship services, and/or other technology transfer services and incubators based within PSL.</p>
	Link to website	https://www.psl.eu/innovation/les-acteurs-de-la-valorisation

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	Is it English-speaking?	Mostly French-speaking (but partly English-speaking)
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd
2.	Name	Mines Paris – PSL coworking space
	Short description	The MINES Paris – PSL coworking space is available to Mines students who are following the entrepreneurship option or who have a business project. The entrepreneurship option is one of fifteen specialization options in the second year. Students who choose this option have two weeks to work on their business project. Several speakers from HEC come during these two weeks to give lectures and organize workshops.
	Link to website	https://psl.eu/en/node/517
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Not likely in the near future
	3.	Name
Short description		The PSL-Lab coworking space provides young entrepreneurs with opportunities for exchange and project collaboration with other students from different PSL institutions. Students have access to many resources and tools which will bring success to their project.
Link to website		https://psl.eu/en/innovation/entrepreneurship-psl/student-entrepreneurship/psl-lab
Is it English-speaking?		Mostly French-speaking (but partly English-speaking)
Is it already open to EELISA partners?		No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?		Tbd

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Table 2: Key startup support institutions and services at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)

3.1.2 Key startup support programs and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)

The following table provides an overview of the key startup support programs and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of nucleation. From the table it can be seen that not every EELISA partner institution has a key startup support program or course on the level of nucleation. From the twelve courses and programs identified five have already been opened to EELISA partners and a few more might be opened in the future. But there are also some key startup support programs and courses that are not English-speaking and some that cannot be opened to EELISA (for example because they are funded by another project).

<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of nucleation at UPM</i>	
1. Name	actúaupm
Short description	ACTÚAUPM, the UPM Entrepreneurship Program, has as its main objective the generation of innovative companies with high growth potential and supporting the entrepreneurial spirit. It develops its work around four pillars: the business idea, the team, the resources that support the project, and the business model that the three previous concepts give rise to. ACTÚAUPM program services are: Follow-up from the initial phase to the establishment of the company; analysis of the feasibility of the project; ongoing advice; guidance in the writing of the business plan; training actions geared to the needs of the team; visibility for investors and support in the search for financing; and the actúaupm Business Creation Competition with already nineteen editions held.
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Zoom
Type of activity	Training
Target group	University entrepreneurs
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	www.upm.es/actuaupm

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	Application deadline	March 21 st 2023
	Date and time of the activity	April – December 2023
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
2.	Name	Introduction to Intra/Social Entrepreneurship
	Short description	Practical course designed for students to discover tools and methodologies for innovators based on new developments and opportunities presented in this new era.
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Zoom
	Type of activity	Training
	Target group	Degree students
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://blogs.upm.es/actividadesacreditables/introduction-to-intra-social-entrepreneurship-c31025/
	Application deadline	30 September 2023
	Date and time of the activity	October – December (every year)
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of nucleation at ENPC</i>		
None		
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of nucleation at FAU</i>		
1.	Name	FAU Digital Tech Fellows Program
	Short description	The Digital Tech Fellows Program is FAU's excellence program open to outstanding digital and innovative talents from all FAU degree programs and faculties! We impart all you need to follow

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	<p>your heart and passion for digitization, entrepreneurship, and innovation. Work in interdisciplinary teams, get in touch with expert coaches and mentors, develop your own pristine and validated business model for your start-up, and get integrated into our Digital Tech Fellows and start-up network & community. For further information, see https://www.dta.fau.de/student-program/.</p>
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	On-site at different locations in Erlangen, Nuremberg, and Waischenfeld as well as some online sessions (for further information, see https://www.dta.fau.de/student-program/)
Type of activity	Excellence program
Target group	Outstanding digital and innovative talents from all FAU degree programs and faculties
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Application for DTF Batch #10 will be possible on the DTF webpage: https://www.dta.fau.de/student-program/
Application deadline	Application for DTF Batch #10 will start in October 2023
Date and time of the activity	Usually from April to July (for the program of 2022, see https://www.dta.fau.de/student-program/)
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
2. Name	Starting Business Ideas @FAU
Short description	<p>Welcome to the workshop series Starting Business Ideas @FAU! Entrepreneur, intrapreneur, freelancer, project team, founding team, start-up?! – this platform is for you. We help you getting started with the Business Design process right away from your idea until the stage where you can start validating your idea. The series consists of six workshops which will take place virtually as Zoom events. Everyone from FAU, Existency, and EELISA can participate. The workshop series consists of several parts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part 0: Ideation Workshop • Part 1: Introduction to Business Design & Value Proposition Creation

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part 2: Business Model Workshop • Part 3: Prototyping – Done is better than perfect! • Part 4: Business Model World Café • Part 5: Financial Modeling Workshop • Part 6: 1-1 Coaching MeetUp <p>For further information, see https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/.</p>
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/
Type of activity	Workshop
Target group	Everybody from EELISA interested in starting business ideas
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	You can take part in each workshop individually concerning your interest and state of development of your founding endeavor. Registration webpage: https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/#collapse_7
Application deadline	The workshops will take place via Zoom. Registration is possible until the last day before each workshop session. But please register as early as possible.
Date and time of the activity	<p>The dates of the workshop sessions can be found on the event webpage: https://www.dta.fau.de/starting-business-ideas-fau/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 27.04.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 0: Ideation Workshop • 09.05.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 1: Introduction to Business Design & Value Proposition Creation • 23.05.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 2: Business Model Workshop • 13.06.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 3: Prototyping • 27.06.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 4: Business Model World Café • 04.07.2023, 16:00-19:00 (CEST): Part 5: Financial Modeling Workshop • 11.07.2023, 16:00-18:00 (CEST): Part 6: 1-1 Coaching Meetup
Is it English-speaking?	Yes

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	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
3.	Name	Impact ³
	Short description	<p>“Impact E³” is the new impact-oriented entrepreneurship qualification program for students and doctoral candidates from all subjects. The aim of the collaborative project from FAU, Ansbach University of Applied Sciences and Weihenstephan-Triesdorf University of Applied Sciences is to develop and implement innovative approaches to solving problems in society and ecology using entrepreneurial thinking and behavior. The format is divided into the following four groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial Impact Basics: A lecture series on sustainable innovation and entrepreneurship as well as an online teaching unit called “Introduction to Sustainability Management”, which focuses on ecologically and socially sustainable impact in a corporate context, provides basic knowledge that participants can build on in subsequent parts of the program. • Entrepreneurial Impact Deep Dive: Here, the impact entrepreneurship potential of students is determined and further developed by teaching basic and advanced knowledge of the individual entrepreneurship topics of social, digital and ecological entrepreneurial impact. • Impact Start-up Garage: The knowledge gained is put into practice during the Entrepreneurial Impact Fellows Program, which is due to start in summer semester 2023. During a qualification program that lasts one semester, students learn methods in fields such as agile business design and sustainable change management that they then apply to impact-related entrepreneurship projects. <p>Entrepreneurial Impact Community: In addition, students receive support for their impact-specific ideas from the start-up consulting service where sustainability mentors advise students and link them with experts from the Ecosystem for Impact Entrepreneurship in Middle Franconia.</p>
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	https://www.fau.eu/outreach/innovation-and-start-ups/successful-start-ups/impact-entrepreneurship/
	Type of activity	Lecture series, workshops, mentoring
	Target group	Students interested in impact entrepreneurship

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Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	See the following link for registration for the various activities: https://www.fau.eu/outreach/innovation-and-start-ups/successful-start-ups/impact-entrepreneurship/
Application deadline	See the following link for the various application deadlines: https://www.fau.eu/outreach/innovation-and-start-ups/successful-start-ups/impact-entrepreneurship/
Date and time of the activity	See the following link for the dates and times of the various activities: https://www.fau.eu/outreach/innovation-and-start-ups/successful-start-ups/impact-entrepreneurship/
Is it English-speaking?	No (in German for the most part)
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Maybe in the future

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of nucleation at ITU

N/A

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of nucleation at SNS

1. Name	Technology transfer in nanotechnologies: IP protection, spin-offs
Short description	The course will cover the basis of innovation exploitation in university and the path of growth and maturation of a spin-off/start up. Teachers from university of the European network EELISA which the school is part, will also be involved. In addition, are awaited contributions from leading companies in the field of innovation: Deloitte, Hoffmann Eitler; while ARTES 4.0 will present as Italian innovation ecosystem.
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	https://www.sns.it/en/avviso/course-technology-transfer-nanotechnologies-ip-protection-spin-offs-prof-guerrini
Type of activity	To provide students with the basic knowledge on University third mission, with a specific emphasis on the opportunities at SNS. To deepen the issues of technology and knowledge transfer, innovation management, patent and IP management, starting a spin-off, tools for enterprise acceleration and support.

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	Target group	PhD students
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	andrea.guerrini@sns.it
	Application deadline	November 2023
	Date and time of the activity	January-April 2024
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of nucleation at SSSA</i>		
1.	Name	High Tech Entrepreneurship Course
	Short description	It's a 20-hours course designed to introduce participants, PhD and undergraduate students from different disciplines (STEM, but also Social Sciences and Humanities) and also young researchers and post-docs, to the basic knowledge and competences about high-tech entrepreneurship.
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Scuola Sant'Anna of Pisa, Piazza Martiri della Libertà, 33 Pisa
	Type of activity	Course
	Target group	PhD students
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Email to uvr@santannapisa.it or to Prof. Andrea Piccaluga a.piccaluga@santannapisa.it
	Application deadline	Tba
	Date and time of the activity	March - May
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes

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Key startup support programs and courses on the level of nucleation at UPB

1.	Name	Entrepreneurship Bootcamp (from UPBizz)
	Short description	Free program for UPB students to introduce them in the entrepreneurship environment, with 6 parts: Economy, Legal, marketing, Management, Financial, Business Plan.
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Online, Microsoft Teams
	Type of activity	Workshop
	Target group	UPB students
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSepIbdHT_EC-KE8QmkRoBH-PVKm8bjLoDUD8sWzNr0wBMeApA/viewform
	Application deadline	April 4
	Date and time of the activity	5 April – 24 May
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Not likely
2.	Name	Grand Challenges Scholars Program (UPBizz)
	Short description	A course aimed for students that trains specialists in various technical fields, who are able to contribute to the technological, economic and socio-cultural progress of the contemporary world. The main strategy aims at the formation of transversal skills, social and relational skills, personal development, orienting the mentality towards engineering solutions that serve the needs of the community and the creation of a multidisciplinary education, through the personal involvement of the beneficiary.
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	UPB, 313 Splaiul Independentei, Bucharest, Romania

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Type of activity	Individual activity and participation at various related events
Target group	2 nd and 3 rd year Bachelor students
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScJiGicVmzjFJMGVJA0RDLdkxjDp_HaqV6CYX8V0bhf_x-nZA/viewform
Application deadline	Still open (not established yet)
Date and time of the activity	Continuous
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Not likely (it is in Romanian, and it requires enrolling as a student at UPB)

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of nucleation at BME

1. Name	BME's Business Express Program
Short description	Register for the BME Business Express Program if you are looking to shorten your startup idea's time to market. The Accelerator complements the HSUP (Hungarian Startup University) courses, resting on similar theoretical foundation. As part of the Accelerator program, you will work hand in hand with mentors and experts to fine tune your idea, to get your team ready to pitch to investors and secure investment to validate your idea.
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Onsite at BME
Type of activity	Startup Accelerator
Target group	PhD, master, academics, researchers, students
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://us3.bme.hu/business-express-program/
Application deadline	5 May 2023

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	Date and time of the activity	9 May 2023 – 15 June 2023
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of nucleation at PSL</i>		
1.	Name	The PSL-Pépité entrepreneurship training program
	Short description	<p>PSL-Pépité is dedicated to all students and young PSL alumni that are looking to work on a project to create a company. It aims to give students the skills, services, and support that they need to realize their project.</p> <p>Open to highly motivated students with entrepreneurship projects, subject to the approval of the academic supervisor, and to alumni. Two main tracks are available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The PSL-Pépité initiation track provides contact with entrepreneurs, the opportunity to attend entrepreneurship events, and to join PSL's entrepreneurship community. • The pre-support path was designed for students who would like to develop an entrepreneurial project alongside their studies, and provides the opportunity to replace required internships with the entrepreneurial project. <p>For further information see: https://www.psl.eu/innovation/entreprendre-psl/entrepreneuriat-etudiant.</p>
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Onsite at PSL (PSL-Lab, 33 rue censier, 75 005 Paris)
	Type of activity	Entrepreneurship activities
	Target group	Students, alumni, and young researchers
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	psl-pepите@psl.eu

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	Application deadline	1st session: June 2nd Session: September 3rd Session: January Each year, we have 3 selection committees.
	Date and time of the activity	1 September to 31 July
	Is it English-speaking?	Most of the program is in French but support can be provided in English.
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd
2.	Name	PSL-iTeams (entrepreneurship awareness program)
	Short description	Established in 2017, the PSL-iTeams academic program is designed to develop your entrepreneurial abilities and help capitalize on the inventions, results and knowledge generated by PSL's research teams through business start-ups or other forms of transfer to the business world and the community. The program will introduce you to the challenges of innovation and provide initial field experience in commercializing research results and starting a company. Participants in the program will be grouped into multidisciplinary teams and given the task of developing a technology transfer strategy (proof of concept, market, business model, etc.) for project concepts. During that process, you'll receive support from professionals in the worlds of business and technology transfer while attending workshops and training modules. For further information, see https://psl.eu/en/node/2121 .
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Onsite at PSL (PSL-Lab, 33 rue censier, 75005 Paris)
	Type of activity	Entrepreneurship awareness program
	Target group	Master's students, PhD students, and Post-docs
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	psl-iteams@psl.eu

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Application deadline	1 st September of each year
Date and time of the activity	October to March (6 months)
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd

Table 3: Key startup support programs and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of nucleation (basic startup skills and knowledge)

3.1.3 Key startup support institutions and services at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of incubation (advanced startup skills and knowledge)

The following table provides an overview of the key startup support institutions and services at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of incubation. From the table it can be seen that every EELISA partner institution has at least one key startup support institution or service on the level of incubation. Some of them have already been opened to EELISA and more can be opened to EELISA in the future. But there are also many key startup support institutions and services that are not English-speaking and some that cannot be opened to EELISA (for example because they are funded by another project).

<i>Key startup support institutions and services on the level of incubation at UPM</i>		
1.	Name	Stage 4 actúaupm
	Short description	Startups receive mentorship, coaching, and access to resources such as funding, office space, and networking opportunities. The goal of this phase is to help startups refine their business models, identify target markets, and develop a scalable growth strategy.
	Link to website	www.upm.es/actuaupm
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No

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	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Possibly next year
2.	Name	Entrepreneurship group UPM
	Short description	The entrepreneurship group UPM is made up of individuals from different centers within UPM. The group is engaged in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Networking and outreach - Fundraising - Business development
	Link to website	There is no website, but there is a contact e-mail address: creacion.empresas@upm.es
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes
3.	Name	Banco Santander (Partnership between UPM & Banco Santander)
	Short description	The partnership involves leveraging the resources and expertise of both organizations to support the creation and growth of innovative new businesses, building partnerships with industry, community engagement, and outreach.
	Link to website	https://www.metaredx.org/global/que-es-metaredx.html
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd
4.	Name	Actúaupm Network of Investors and Experts
	Short description	The Actúaupm Network of Investors and Experts is a community of individuals who come together to support the growth and development of innovative new businesses. This network is typically composed of investors, who provide funding and financial support to startups, and experts, who offer mentorship,

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	guidance, and industry-specific knowledge to help entrepreneurs succeed. By leveraging the resources and expertise of this network, startups can access the funding, mentorship, and support they need to navigate the challenges of launching and growing a new business. The Network of Investors and Experts is a vital part of the innovation ecosystem, helping to support the development of new technologies, products, and services that have the potential to transform industries and drive economic growth.
Link to website	www.upm.es/actuaupm
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of incubation at ENPC

1. Name	Incubateur Descartes
Short description	<p>Do you have a technology-intensive business project? Do you want to exploit research results? Is your project in the field of Greentech Sustainable Cities, New Digital Services or Health & Society? Benefit from the dynamics of Cité Descartes' ecosystem East of the new Greater Paris!</p> <p>Descartes Développement & Innovation incubator team guides you to success. Incubateur Descartes is a support service to help in the creation of innovative startups with high technological added value. This service is labelled EU-BIC (European Union Business Innovation Centre). Cité Descartes Incubator, it is located at the heart of the Excellence pole for Sustainable City of Paris-Vallée de la Marne, close to Gustave Eiffel University. We coach project founders from the advanced idea stage (structured as a draft business plan) to proof of concept, from the definition of a product/market fit to a viable business & financial plan. Incubateur Descartes targets would be entrepreneurs: researchers & professors, economic stakeholders and young graduates (especially PhDs).</p>
Link to website	https://www.descartes-devinnov.com/incubateur-descartes/
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No

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	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
2.	Name	d.school Paris
	Short description	The mission of the d.school Paris of École des Ponts ParisTech is to pass on the methods of design innovation through practice in order to inspire the actors of tomorrow's world. For 12 years, d.school Paris has been promoting Design Thinking as an approach to innovation and its management. This way of thinking, of conceiving and approaching problems is conducive to generating new sources of innovation and implementing sustainable solutions. Over the past two years, d.school Paris has broadened its skills and know-how by incorporating other design practices such as fictional design and sustainable design into its learning methods. These different design approaches add to creativity, collaboration and iteration - already strongly developed in Design Thinking - the key notions of anticipation, new narratives, strategy and action with Design Fiction as well as sobriety, evaluation and decision making with Sustainable Design. If these two approaches respectively meet the needs of exploration and reinvention of possible futures on the one hand, and the needs of sustainability of innovations and action to be generated on the other hand, they aim to combine with our Design Thinking approach. By developing these three competencies, d.school Paris aims to experiment with a new, unique, more global approach, taking into account in its reflection innovation with all its stakes, both for humans and for the future they conceive for themselves and the world they inhabit.
	Link to website	https://ecoledesponts.fr/dschool-paris
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	In principle yes (but the design thinking courses offered by d.school are fee-based)
3.	Name	Station F
	Short description	ENPC offers 31 places for selected startups of its students, researchers or alumni in the world's largest startup campus in Paris.
	Link to website	https://stationf.co/services
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes

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	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
4.	Name	Co-Innovation Lab ENPC
	Short description	The Co-Innovation Lab at ENPC consists of three different well-equipped platforms in order to accelerate research and innovation: La Plateforme Build'in, la Plateforme Fresnel and la Plateforme Mu.
	Link to website	https://ecoledesponts.fr/co-innovation-lab
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of incubation at FAU

1.	Name	ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator
	Short description	Do you have a great idea, an initial concept, maybe also a prototype and a strong team with which you'd like to start a company? Then you should put your ideas to the 'start-up test' and have your proposal evaluated. ZOLLHOF, the digital start-up centre at FAU, is the right place for you. With the help of talented entrepreneurs, you will quickly learn how you can turn your idea into a market-ready innovation or set up your own company. The digital start-up centre ZOLLHOF offers comprehensive support to start-ups in areas such as the Internet of Things, smart city and big data. It was set up in Nuremberg on FAU's initiative. Those starting their own companies can hire open office space including infrastructure, and are given practical assistance in developing their products and services, benefiting from connections to an extensive network of companies and entrepreneurs cooperating with ZOLLHOF.
	Link to website	www.zollhof.de/
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes

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	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
2.	Name	JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab
	Short description	Would you like to develop innovations yourself? Then JOSEPHS®, the open innovation lab in Nuremberg city centre, is just the place for you. JOSEPHS® offers both individuals and entire organisations an exciting range of services for innovation.
	Link to website	https://josephs-innovation.de/wp/
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
3.	Name	NKubator
	Short description	<p>Workshops, laboratories, prototypes: On a floor area of 480 square meters in the former AEG premises in Nuremberg, the “NKubator” is available to help boost the sustainability of your start-up, both when it comes to the company itself as well as when developing products and ideas. The IdeenWerk package is aimed at sparking the creativity of founders and their staff, Startup Werk offers floor space and support for green start-ups and SustainAbility helps start-ups develop sustainable business activities.</p> <p>NKubator is funded by the city of Nuremberg. It is operated by ENERGIEregion Nürnberg e.V., a skills and cluster initiative committed to the topics of energy and environment in the Nuremberg Metropolitan Region. Other project partners behind the NKubator are the Department for Economic Development at the city of Nuremberg, the Institute for Factory Automation and Production Systems (FAPS) at FAU and Energieagentur Nordbayern GmbH. All the partners have many years’ experience in supporting start-ups in the region and have strong ties to research and industry for encouraging sustainable success.</p>
	Link to website	www.nkubator.eu/

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	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
4.	Name	LZE (Leistungszentrum Elektroniksysteme)
	Short description	<p>For when things really start getting serious, you can choose to work with professionals from large corporations and medium-sized business to develop high-performance products and processes in the context of real entrepreneurial innovation. LZE is the right place for you in this case.</p> <p>The High-Performance Centre builds on the many years of intense collaboration between the Fraunhofer Institutes and FAU as well as the unique concentration of research and industry in the field of electronic systems in Erlangen and the surrounding Nuremberg Metropolitan Region. Excellent research and joint planning form the basis for an extensive long-term strategic partnership between Fraunhofer, FAU and industry. The pilot phase for the High Performance Centre for Electronic Systems started in January 2015 and is funded by the Bavarian State Ministry of Economic Affairs and Media, Energy and Technology.</p>
	Link to website	www.lze.bayern/
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
5.	Name	Medical Valley
	Short description	<p>Medical Valley accelerates time to market for healthcare innovations. It is one of the strongest, most active medical technology research clusters in the world. Renowned partners from industry, research, healthcare and politics have come together to form this interdisciplinary network. Their common goal is to come up with successful solutions for the healthcare of tomorrow.</p> <p>The year 2010 showed just how outstanding the structures in Medical Valley are, as the German Ministry of Education and</p>

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	<p>Research (BMBF) chose Medical Valley EMN as a national Leading Edge Cluster upon its application as a 'Centre of Excellence for Medical Engineering'.</p> <p>Medical engineering products and services are currently being developed in over 40 projects. These products and services are aimed at making prevention, diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation in connection with a variety of illnesses more efficient and more effective. Activities in the cluster and communication among the stakeholders are coordinated by the Medical Valley EMN Association, which also supports its members with numerous services.</p> <p>FAU is a member of Medical Valley and has close connections to many of its partners thanks to its research projects. Furthermore, research and teaching in this field have become a well-established part of the University through the Central Institute of Healthcare Engineering and the medical technology degree programme.</p>
Link to website	https://www.medical-valley-emn.de/en/
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
6. Name	EXISTENCY
Short description	EXISTENCY is a joint project of Ansbach University of Applied Sciences, Nuremberg University of Technology and Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg to promote start-ups at universities. The project is funded by the EXIST-Potentials program of the Federal Ministry of Economics and Climate Protection.
Link to website	https://www.existency.de/
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No

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Key startup support institutions and services on the level of incubation at ITU

1. Name	ITUCekirdek
Short description	ITUCekirdek is the top university-based incubator in the world according to UBI Global ranking and offers various services to support Turkish and global startups. Basic services include startup training, mentoring, free or substantially subsidized cloud services and applications, prototyping lab, stipend money for prototyping costs. In its pre-incubation and incubation programs, it hosts more than 500 technology-based startups annually.
Link to website	https://itucekirdek.com/en/home/
Is it English-speaking?	There is one program (ITUSEED) running in English.
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	ITUSEED is already open for EELISA partners

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of incubation at SNS

1. Name	Agreement and collaboration with POLO TECNOLOGICO NAVACCHIO
Short description	Scouting, visibility, networking, investors' search, identification of calls for proposals and funding, choice of financial solutions, training, internationalization and commercial support are just some of the services Polo provides to its enterprises, which can always count on a team to share, expand and improve their business projects and grow new ideas.
Link to website	https://www.polotecnologico.it/en/
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of incubation at SSSA

1. Name	JUMP (Joint Universities prograM for Poc)
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Short description	<p>JUMP (Joint Universities prograM for Poc) is the program of the Scuola Sant'Anna, of the Scuola Normale and the University of Palermo that has been found eligible for a €325,000 grant from the Ministry of Economic Development for patent enhancement and funding of Proof of Concept projects.</p> <p>With the JUMP program, the partners have the underlying goal of attempting to valorize some of the most innovative and promising patented technologies that are at the same time more immature from a developmental point of view, intervening to stimulate on the one hand research groups so that they commit their expertise to the advancement of the technology, and on the other hand external parties to invest in industrial development.</p>
Link to website	http://www.jump-poc.it/it
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of incubation at UPB

1. Name	Innovation Labs
Short description	<p>Innovation Labs is a pre-accelerator for young tech founders and startups. The program targets students and graduates from technical universities and from communication, business and creative fields for the 3-month mentoring adventure of teamwork, intensive prototype development and mentorship, exploring Romania's growing startup ecosystem. The pre-accelerator has predominant activities within the University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest (mentioned in many of their press releases). Innovation Labs offers students (and even more experienced researchers and developers) the chance to pitch their ideas and participate in a pre-accelerator that can lead them on the path of getting an investment in their product. The participants are empowered to develop proof-of-concept solutions and products using cutting edge tech with the support of top mentors in the ICT and business industry. The teams accepted in the program will work during the mentoring program to develop prototypes for their idea through user testing, design work, business modelling and product validation in weekly courses and workshops in a variety of fields. Innovation Labs gives participants the chance to</p>

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	take part in demo days, hackathons, presentations in front of potential investors, etc.
Link to website	https://www.innovationlabs.ro
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	It is open to anyone.
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes, it has a potential to be internationalized.

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of incubation at BME

1. Name	BME US(3)
Short description	BME US(3) is the incubator of the University of Technology & Economics in Budapest. Our Startup Spinoff Studio is created to foster university-based innovation and boost the entrepreneurial mindset within academia. Team US(3) works in co-operation with corporates and investors to ignite the flourishing potential at the university.
Link to website	https://us3.bme.hu/
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of incubation at PSL

1. Name	Incubateur Paris-Dauphine
Short description	The Paris-Dauphine Incubator develops and supports the entrepreneurial spirit at Dauphine-PSL, and generally at PSL, among students and graduates, through a triple objective: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raising awareness of entrepreneurship • Supporting entrepreneurs • Unite an ecosystem
Link to website	https://www.psl.eu/en/node/519 https://dauphine.psl.eu/vie-de-campus/incubateur

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	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd
2.	Name	PC Up
	Short description	<p>Supporting the creation of companies, PC Up is the incubator of the ESPCI Paris. Supported by the City of Paris since 2014, PC Up creates an average of 3 start-ups per year, providing access to a high-level scientific environment and to equipment made available to them on the ESPCI Paris – PSL and IPGG sites.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to technical equipment: clean room, grey room, especially adapted to microfluidics • Acceleration or co-incubation program with Agoranov, Institut de la Vision, Paris Biotech Santé, Paris & Co • Recruitment of interns from ESPCI – PSL <p>50% of project leaders are post-doctoral students and 50% are from the corporate world. 60% of the technologies involved are in the field of microfluidics and the rest concern other fields of physics, chemistry, engineering, and life sciences (notably wave physics for medicine).</p>
	Link to website	https://www.psl.eu/en/node/547 https://www.espci.psl.eu/fr/innovation/l-incubateur-pc-up/
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd
3.	Name	Chimie Paris Innov
	Short description	<p>Thanks to the support of the Ile-de-France Region and funding from the European community, Chimie ParisTech - PSL has had, since 2017, a complete structure focused on business creation: Chimie Paris Innov.</p>
	Link to website	https://www.chimieparistech.psl.eu/entreprise-innovation/incuber-son-entreprise-a-chimie-paristech/

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	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd
4.	Name	PSL Tech Seed
	Short description	<p>The PSL Tech Seed initiative provides tech start-ups from PSL and Institut Pasteur that are supported by one or more private investors (business angels, venture capitalists, manufacturers, etc.) with access to joint financing from BPIFrance via the French Tech Seed fund.</p> <p>In order to support tech start-ups in their post-maturation or pre-seed stage, the French government's "Investments for the Future" program endowed the French Tech Seed investment fund with €400 million. To be eligible, start-ups must first have been certified by consortia approved by BPIFrance, such as PSL Tech Seed.</p> <p>The PSL Tech Seed consortium, which is sponsored by PSL and includes Institut Pasteur, was one of the first grantees and became a certified referrer in January 2019. This status was renewed in early 2021 for a period of 2 years.</p> <p>PSL Tech Seed is open to all PSL and Institut Pasteur startups, across all disciplines and fields of application. It will serve as a force multiplier for the private funding obtained by these start-ups, with a major impact on their development.</p>
	Link to website	https://www.psl.eu/en/innovation/entrepreneurship-psl/psl-tech-seed
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No

Table 3: Key startup support institutions and services at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of incubation (advanced startup skills and knowledge)

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3.1.4 Key startup support programs and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of incubation (advanced startup skills and knowledge)

The following table provides an overview of the key startup support programs and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of incubation. From the table it can be seen that most, but not all, EELISA partner institutions do have at least one key startup support program or course on the level of incubation. Almost half of the programs and courses have already been opened to EELISA and more can be opened to EELISA in the future. But there are also some key startup support programs and courses that are not English-speaking and at least one program that cannot be opened to EELISA (because it is funded by another project).

<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of incubation at UPM</i>		
1.	Name	Stage 4 training
	Short description	Stage 4 training consists of specific sessions to prepare a small group of start-ups to reach the next stage of the business model.
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	On site
	Type of activity	Entrepreneurship and mentorship
	Target group	Start-ups
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Creacion.empresas@upm.es
	Application deadline	tba
	Date and time of the activity	January - September
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd
2.	Name	UPM TT Course

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Short description	UPM TT is a 10-weeks online programme that aims to support researchers and high-tech entrepreneurs on their way to validate a successful business based on technology. We want you to tackle the key challenges you must face when validating your innovative project in terms of business value. By acquiring advanced skills, knowing new tools and approaches or getting access to our ecosystem, you will be challenged to structure your market validation while testing your value proposition. Get in touch with industry experts, investors, and entrepreneurs for a direct access to market know-how and stay connected from now on.
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	https://www.upm.es/S2i/fdin/index.jsp?alias=INNOVATECH-2020
Type of activity	Training
Target group	Researchers
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Tba
Application deadline	September (every year)
Date and time of the activity	October – February (every year)
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of incubation at ENPC

1. Name	d.school Paris: Programme ME310
Short description	In the course of a full-time academic year, three multidisciplinary teams of four students each, located at d.school and in an institution belonging to the international network headed by Stanford University (including HPI Potsdam in Germany and Aalto University's Design Factory in Finland), innovate from a realworld brief, with high strategic stakes, brought by an industrial

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	partner and entailing the reinvention of a product/service in a potential growth market. For further information, see https://me310.paris/en/ .
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	D.school Paris, 8-10 Av. Blaise Pascal, 77420 Champs-sur-Marne
Type of activity	One year full time program (master level)
Target group	Graduates in engineering and from other disciplines
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	Application is possible via e-mail (contact@dschool.fr) or online (www.me310.paris).
Application deadline	31 May each year
Date and time of the activity	End of September until end of June each year
Is it English-speaking?	French and English
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	In principle yes (but the program costs between 2.500 € and 3.300 €)

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of incubation at FAU

1. Name	ZOLLHOF Talent Program
Short description	With our 3-month digital innovation program (20h / week), you can explore and experience how startups innovate and apply the Design Thinking framework to tackle real-world challenges of large corporations. Develop your out-of-the-box solution in an interdisciplinary team with complete ownership. Work on topics such as e-mobility, digital health and IoT... Your ZOLLHOF coach and innovation workshops support you to live up to your full potential.
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	ZOLLHOF, Zollhof 7, 90443 Nürnberg, Germany
Type of activity	Talent program
Target group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students with all study backgrounds and interests (e.g. Business, IT, Engineering, Design, Marketing, Psychology, Health)

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest in tech topics • Open and positive spirit • Solution-oriented mindset • Confident use of the German and English language necessary
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.zollhof.de/talent
Application deadline	Application is always possible.
Date and time of the activity	Date and time will be announced after the application.
Is it English-speaking?	partly
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Not yet
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Probably
2. Name	ZOLLHOF Startup Incubation Program
Short description	<p>At ZOLLHOF we are all about paving the way for people with a positive entrepreneurial mindset who want to create the new. We believe in working together collaboratively in order to accelerate value-driven human-centered business models. Since 2017 90 startups have participated in our incubation program and raised more than 243 million EUR in venture capital while signing thousands of customers. Why don't you come and join us?</p> <p>Your startup and your team are unique. This is why we designed a highly personalized 6 months incubation program for early stage startups that caters exactly to your current needs. In order to support your idea to take off you'll learn from our inhouse experts as well as our extensive network. Become a part of one of Germany's fastest growing entrepreneurship ecosystems now!</p>
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	ZOLLHOF, Zollhof 7, 90443 Nürnberg, Germany
Type of activity	Startup Incubation Program
Target group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative early stage startups that are able to move fast • Complementary teams with a positive spirit • Ideas that solve real life problems

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	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.zollhof.de/startup-incubation
	Application deadline	Application is always possible.
	Date and time of the activity	Date and time will be announced after the application.
	Is it English-speaking?	Partly
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Not yet
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Probably
3.	Name	Medical Valley Services for Startups
	Short description	<p>We offer customized services for all startup stages and beyond – from the first steps to business formation to the international market entry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Startup consulting: We have been consulting founders in the healthcare and medical technology sector since 2003. With our know-how and partner network we help you define your business plan. - Incubator & office space: Together with our incubators Medical Valley Center Erlangen and Medical Valley Center Forchheim we offer high-growth companies in the healthcare industry excellent office space in one of the economically strongest and scientifically most active healthcare clusters worldwide – the Medical Valley European Metropolitan Region Nuremberg. A total of almost 7,000 m² of flexible and representative office space is available. In the Medical Valley Centers in Erlangen and Forchheim, you will sit alongside with other startups and growth companies and have daily access to our Medical Valley team and service portfolio. - Access to healthcare-specific startup programs: In the last few years many startup programs have been established: bootcamps, hackathons, business plan competitions or accelerator programs. We help you identify the right ones for your respective business situation. - Venture capital: We support you in finding the right investors for your company – during all startup stages and beyond. We are connected to relevant healthcare investors, such as angel investors, VC funds, corporate VCs or equity crowdfunding providers.

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acquisition of funds: For you, we scout for the right funding programs at state, federal and EU level. Since 2010, we have raised more than 150 million € in funding for our partners. - Access to strategic partners: We are directly linked to partners in industry, research, healthcare and politics, so we can introduce you to potential business partners. - Venture building: If you are looking for suitable partners to bring your idea or startup to life, Medical Valley GmbH can co-found startups as a startup factory. This means, for example, if you are a doctor or researcher with ideas that are ready for commercialization, but you wish to remain a doctor or researcher, we can – in selected cases -, jointly found a startup. In the last three years we have actively participated in three medical technology startups and have taken on management duties. - Certification, approval, reimbursement: To successfully launch your medical device on the market, a precise and accurate planning of your regulatory strategy is indispensable. We will provide guidance to help you find the right person for the approval of your product. Moreover, we can also help you with your reimbursement strategy. We are affiliated with numerous public and private health insurance companies in Germany and offer unique medical, technical and health economic validation support with our dmac (Digital Medical Application Center). - Internationalization: Are you looking for a way to access international markets? We make sure that you don't have to go down this road alone by determining potential markets in advance and transparently highlighting relevant conditions. Market analysis, development of regulatory strategies and on-site visits help you to develop a comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and challenges of the target country. If you are interested in entering the German market, we are also there to assist you. We can provide you with essential information about the German market and the healthcare system and work out the optimal project plan together with you. <p>You don't know where to start? Are you looking for impulses, inspiration, answers or the right questions? If you don't know what you need to bring your startup forward or if you are interested in topics that are not listed here, please, feel free to contact us.</p>
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	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	https://www.medical-valley-emn.de/en/ourservices/services-for-startups/
	Type of activity	Various services for startups in the health sector
	Target group	Startups from the health sector
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.medical-valley-emn.de/en/ourservices/services-for-startups/
	Application deadline	Application is always possible.
	Date and time of the activity	Ongoing activities
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
4.	Name	EXISTENCY Reality Bites
	Short description	At some point, you really want it. Starting a business. With this idea. With this team. Now. Reality Bites helps you and your team really to get your idea on the road now. We focus on what is really important: Proximity to reality. Because all theories, all methods, all knowledge are useless if you can't apply them. In the Building Box as well as in the Test UGs, we accompany you and your founding team over several months, provide you with mentors, experienced founders and coaches and help you with one thing above all: to get started. And to make what you have already done even better. The crowdfunding contest is also about getting active and making progress - but the focus here is more on the financial aspect. And what does it look like when reality bites?
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	https://www.existency.de/reality-bites/
	Type of activity	Incubation programs
	Target group	Early-stage startups
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.existency.de/reality-bites/

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Application deadline	See https://www.existency.de/reality-bites/ for the various application deadlines.
Date and time of the activity	See https://www.existency.de/reality-bites/ for the various application deadlines.
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of incubation at ITU

1. Name	ITU SEED Acceleration Program
Short description	ITU SEED Acceleration Program boosts startups to go global with countless opportunities in one of the best metropolises in the world: Istanbul. What is ITU SEED International Startup Accelerator? At ITU SEED, we hosted thousands of startups over the past 10 years and accompanied them in their global success stories. Join us at the ITU SEED International Startup Accelerator! Develop your early-stage company, take advantage of countless opportunities and fast-track commercializing your products at one of the top 5 university-affiliated incubation centers in the world. For further information, see https://ituseed.com/ .
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Istanbul, Turkey (certain sessions of the program are online and the links will be delivered directly to the eligible participants)
Type of activity	Acceleration program (training, mentoring, investor demo day, perks)
Target group	Global startups with a short run objective to expand their activities internationally, especially with a particular focus on Turkish market.
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://ituseed.com/preliminary-application/
Application deadline	April 26 th , 2023

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	Date and time of the activity	Late June-Mid August, 2023
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of incubation at SNS</i>		
None		
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of incubation at SSSA</i>		
None		
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of incubation at UPB</i>		
1.	Name	Innovation Labs Hackathon and Pre-Acceleration Phases
	Short description	Innovation Labs offers, as the starting point of the journey, selection hackathons that end up with pitches of the ideas that can move further on. Afterwards, selected proposals go to the pre-acceleration phase, where they attend weekly workshops and inspirational tech-talks sessions that engage them with the entrepreneurial ecosystem and provide food for thought. Empowered by mentors and assigned coaches, the participants will be assisted in developing their product on various dimensions (with workshops on topics such as planning an MVP, fast prototyping, business models, etc.).
	Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Bucharest, Brasov, Sibiu (Romania)
	Type of activity	Hackathons and workshops
	Target group	Students, university research groups, senior teams
	Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.innovationlabs.ro/program
	Application deadline	February (yearly)
	Date and time of the activity	December – May (yearly)

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Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	It is open to anyone.
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes, most likely

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of incubation at BME

1. Name	BME US(3)
Short description	BME US(3) provides coworking space and a fablab for early stage startups, in addition to ongoing mentoring.
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	On site at BME
Type of activity	BME US(3) provides coworking space and a fablab for early stage startups, in addition to ongoing mentoring.
Target group	Early stage startups
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	szatmari.peter@bme.hu
Application deadline	N/A
Date and time of the activity	Ongoing
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of incubation at PSL

1. Name	Incubation Programs at the Incubator Paris-Dauphine
Short description	<p>Created in 2012, the Incubator Paris-Dauphine offers three business-oriented incubation programs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Program for graduates in Paris • Program for students in Paris • Graduate program in London <p>For further information see:</p>

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	https://www.psl.eu/incubateur-paris-dauphine
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Paris and London (on-site)
Type of activity	Incubation programs
Target group	Early-stage start-ups
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.psl.eu/incubateur-paris-dauphine
Application deadline	Tba
Date and time of the activity	Tba
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd

Table 5: Key startup support programs and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of incubation (advanced startup skills and knowledge)

3.1.5 Key startup support institutions and services at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of acceleration (professional startup skills and knowledge)

The following table provides an overview of the key startup support institutions and services at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of acceleration. From the table it can be seen that some, but not all, EELISA partner institutions have key startup support institutions or services on the level of acceleration. Most of them have already been opened to EELISA and possibly two more can be opened to EELISA in the future. But there are also some key startup support institutions and services that are not English-speaking and at least one that cannot be opened to EELISA (because it is funded by another project).

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of acceleration at UPM

1. Name	Inspiring Women
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Short description	It is a gathering that provides support and resources for women entrepreneurs. The event is designed to accelerate the growth and development of female-led businesses by offering mentorship, training, and access to funding and other resources. Through networking opportunities, panel discussions, and workshops, female entrepreneurs can learn from successful business leaders, gain valuable insights, and connect with investors and industry experts
Link to website	https://www.eventbrite.com/e/entradas-inspiring-women-leaders-in-the-digital-era-609283823317
Is it English-speaking?	No (subtitles)
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of acceleration at ENPC

None

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of acceleration at FAU

1. Name	ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator
Short description	Do you have a great idea, an initial concept, maybe also a prototype and a strong team with which you'd like to start a company? Then you should put your ideas to the 'start-up test' and have your proposal evaluated. ZOLLHOF, the digital start-up centre at FAU, is the right place for you. With the help of talented entrepreneurs, you will quickly learn how you can turn your idea into a market-ready innovation or set up your own company. The digital start-up centre ZOLLHOF offers comprehensive support to start-ups in areas such as the Internet of Things, smart city and big data. It was set up in Nuremberg on FAU's initiative. Those starting their own companies can hire open office space including infrastructure, and are given practical assistance in developing their products and services, benefiting from connections to an extensive network of companies and entrepreneurs cooperating with ZOLLHOF.
Link to website	www.zollhof.de/
Is it English-speaking?	Yes

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	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
2.	Name	JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab
	Short description	Would you like to develop innovations yourself? Then JOSEPHS®, the open innovation lab in Nuremberg city centre, is just the place for you. JOSEPHS® offers both individuals and entire organisations an exciting range of services for innovation.
	Link to website	https://josephs-innovation.de/wp/
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
3.	Name	Medical Valley
	Short description	<p>Medical Valley accelerates time to market for healthcare innovations. It is one of the strongest, most active medical technology research clusters in the world. Renowned partners from industry, research, healthcare and politics have come together to form this interdisciplinary network. Their common goal is to come up with successful solutions for the healthcare of tomorrow.</p> <p>The year 2010 showed just how outstanding the structures in Medical Valley are, as the German Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) chose Medical Valley EMN as a national Leading Edge Cluster upon its application as a 'Centre of Excellence for Medical Engineering'.</p> <p>Medical engineering products and services are currently being developed in over 40 projects. These products and services are aimed at making prevention, diagnosis, treatment and rehabilitation in connection with a variety of illnesses more efficient and more effective. Activities in the cluster and communication among the stakeholders are coordinated by the Medical Valley EMN Association, which also supports its members with numerous services.</p> <p>FAU is a member of Medical Valley and has close connections to many of its partners thanks to its research projects. Furthermore,</p>

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		research and teaching in this field have become a well-established part of the University through the Central Institute of Healthcare Engineering and the medical technology degree programme.
	Link to website	https://www.medical-valley-emn.de/en/
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes (partly)
4.	Name	EXISTENCY
	Short description	EXISTENCY is a joint project of Ansbach University of Applied Sciences, Nuremberg University of Technology and Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg to promote start-ups at universities. The project is funded by the EXIST-Potentials program of the Federal Ministry of Economics and Climate Protection.
	Link to website	https://www.existency.de/
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
<i>Key startup support institutions and services on the level of acceleration at ITU</i>		
1.	Name	ITU ARI Teknokent (including ITU MAGNET)
	Short description	ITU ARI Teknokent (Science Park) has been founded on an area of 1,655,000 m ² with 10 buildings, enabling over 2800 successful R&D projects (148 of which patented) and \$40 million exports to contribute to the national economy in Turkey. Today at ITU ARI Teknokent, more than 290 R&D companies have reached a total of \$1 billion turnovers with over 7000 employees to develop more than 600 projects annually.

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	<p>ITU ARI Teknokent believes in “planting culture” and “value-adding” through its activities and the programs developed. ITU ARI Teknokent focuses on improving its brands ITU Çekirdek, Big Bang, ITU MAGNET, Innogate, Beetech, and supports and values brands of its shareholders to lead them to a brighter future.</p> <p>Founded by ITU ARI Teknokent in 2017 on 2000 m2 area to serve up to 76 scale ups, ITU MAGNET provides services 24/7, containing a prototyping lab, a common-use event stage (Magnetic Field), a total number of 10 seminar halls and meeting rooms, a self-service unmanned shop and a 4-season garden.</p> <p>ITU MAGNET is positioned as...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a hub for venture firms that already received initial investment, generate similar resources with their revenue, or need VC-level investments to be in the phase of growth or for further growth, within entrepreneurial ecosystem in Turkey, • a hub where corporate firms associate with select entrepreneurs to develop collaboration and manage their own start-up programs, • the first “Late-Stage Entrepreneurship Center” in Turkey with an aim to be the “soft-landing” hub for foreign start-ups that want to grow in Istanbul.
Link to website	<p>https://www.ariteknokent.com.tr/en For further information about ITU MAGNET, see https://www.ariteknokent.com.tr/en/ecosystem/itu-magnet and https://itumagnet.com/en/homepage/. For further information about ITU Innogate, see https://www.ariteknokent.com.tr/en/ecosystem/innogate and https://innogate.org/en/homepage/.</p>
Is it English-speaking?	Both Turkish & English
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	tbd
<i>Key startup support institutions and services on the level of acceleration at SNS</i>	
None	

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Key startup support institutions and services on the level of acceleration at SSSA

1.	Name	Joint Technology Transfer Office – JoTTO
	Short description	JoTTO is the joint Technology Transfer Office of the six Schools of Excellence in Italy aiming at creating critical mass, sharing best practices, and organizing joint match-making events between researchers and companies or investors.
	Link to website	http://www.jointto.it/en
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
2.	Name	Third Mission Administrative Area (Third Mission Office)
	Short description	The SSSA recently established a Third Mission Office that encompasses the former Research Results Exploitation Services and at the same time widens and enriches the offer of services to aspiring entrepreneurs while providing tailored services to start-ups and spin-offs. The accelerating effect has been fostered through a comprehensive and extended network whose major benefits have been spread through the network of SSSA spin-offs. They have seen a multiplying effect in their market outputs while widening their connections and strengthening their international relations. The Third Mission area has joined forces with the major investors and stakeholders, so to enhance the acceleration process and readiness for market. Bigger players have been reached: for instance, a venture with the major Italian public investor has been put in place with the aim of accelerating the start-ups operating in Robotics and AI (Robo.it).
	Link to website	https://www.santannapisa.it/en/outreach-impact/outreach-and-impact-santanna-school For contact persons see: https://www.santannapisa.it/en/node/5816
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes

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Key startup support institutions and services on the level of acceleration at UPB

1.	Name	Innovation Labs
	Short description	Innovation Labs is a pre-accelerator for young tech founders and startups. But it also offers some of the functionalities of an accelerator, such as access to its network including investors, long-term support for its startups, and also advice on applying for specialized accelerators.
	Link to website	https://www.innovationlabs.ro
	Is it English-speaking?	No
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	It is open to anyone.
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes, it has a potential to be internationalized.

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of acceleration at BME

None

Key startup support institutions and services on the level of acceleration at PSL

1.	Name	PSL Innovation Fund
	Short description	PSL has joined forces with Elaia Partners to create a seed investment fund dedicated to startups in its ecosystem. PSL and Elaia have raised €76 million from public and private investors, well beyond their initial objective. They are working together to detect, evaluate and support high-potential projects that will become the champions of tomorrow. The Fund holds equity in a highly promising portfolio, comprising 20 deep-tech startups.
	Link to website	https://psl.eu/innovation/entreprendre-psl/psl-innovation-fund
	Is it English-speaking?	Yes
	Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
	Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd

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Table 6: Key startup support institutions and services at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of acceleration (professional startup skills and knowledge)

3.1.6 Key startup support programs and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of acceleration (professional startup skills and knowledge)

The following table provides an overview of the key startup support programs and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of acceleration. From the table it can be seen that just a few EELISA partner institutions have key startup support programs or courses on the level of acceleration and most partners don't. One of these programs and courses has already been opened to EELISA and three others might be opened to EELISA in the future. But one of them is not English-speaking and at least another one cannot be opened to EELISA (because it is funded by another project).

<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of acceleration at UPM</i>					
None					
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of acceleration at ENPC</i>					
None					
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of acceleration at FAU</i>					
1.	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Name</td> <td>Medical Valley Services for Startups</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Short description</td> <td> <p>We offer customized services for all startup stages and beyond – from the first steps to business formation to the international market entry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Startup consulting: We have been consulting founders in the healthcare and medical technology sector since 2003. With our know-how and partner network we help you define your business plan. - Incubator & office space: Together with our incubators Medical Valley Center Erlangen and Medical Valley Center Forchheim we offer high-growth companies in the healthcare industry excellent office space in one of the economically strongest and scientifically most active healthcare clusters worldwide – the Medical Valley European Metropolitan Region Nuremberg. A total of almost 7,000 m² of flexible and representative office space is available. In the Medical Valley Centers in </td> </tr> </table>	Name	Medical Valley Services for Startups	Short description	<p>We offer customized services for all startup stages and beyond – from the first steps to business formation to the international market entry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Startup consulting: We have been consulting founders in the healthcare and medical technology sector since 2003. With our know-how and partner network we help you define your business plan. - Incubator & office space: Together with our incubators Medical Valley Center Erlangen and Medical Valley Center Forchheim we offer high-growth companies in the healthcare industry excellent office space in one of the economically strongest and scientifically most active healthcare clusters worldwide – the Medical Valley European Metropolitan Region Nuremberg. A total of almost 7,000 m² of flexible and representative office space is available. In the Medical Valley Centers in
Name	Medical Valley Services for Startups				
Short description	<p>We offer customized services for all startup stages and beyond – from the first steps to business formation to the international market entry.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Startup consulting: We have been consulting founders in the healthcare and medical technology sector since 2003. With our know-how and partner network we help you define your business plan. - Incubator & office space: Together with our incubators Medical Valley Center Erlangen and Medical Valley Center Forchheim we offer high-growth companies in the healthcare industry excellent office space in one of the economically strongest and scientifically most active healthcare clusters worldwide – the Medical Valley European Metropolitan Region Nuremberg. A total of almost 7,000 m² of flexible and representative office space is available. In the Medical Valley Centers in 				

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		<p>Erlangen and Forchheim, you will sit alongside with other startups and growth companies and have daily access to our Medical Valley team and service portfolio.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Access to healthcare-specific startup programs: In the last few years many startup programs have been established: bootcamps, hackathons, business plan competitions or accelerator programs. We help you identify the right ones for your respective business situation. - Venture capital: We support you in finding the right investors for your company – during all startup stages and beyond. We are connected to relevant healthcare investors, such as angel investors, VC funds, corporate VCs or equity crowdfunding providers. - Acquisition of funds: For you, we scout for the right funding programs at state, federal and EU level. Since 2010, we have raised more than 150 million € in funding for our partners. - Access to strategic partners: We are directly linked to partners in industry, research, healthcare and politics, so we can introduce you to potential business partners. - Venture building: If you are looking for suitable partners to bring your idea or startup to life, Medical Valley GmbH can co-found startups as a startup factory. This means, for example, if you are a doctor or researcher with ideas that are ready for commercialization, but you wish to remain a doctor or researcher, we can – in selected cases -, jointly found a startup. In the last three years we have actively participated in three medical technology startups and have taken on management duties. - Certification, approval, reimbursement: To successfully launch your medical device on the market, a precise and accurate planning of your regulatory strategy is indispensable. We will provide guidance to help you find the right person for the approval of your product. Moreover, we can also help you with your reimbursement strategy. We are affiliated with numerous public and private health insurance companies in Germany and offer unique medical, technical and health economic validation support with our dmac (Digital Medical Application Center). - Internationalization: Are you looking for a way to access international markets? We make sure that you don't have to go down this road alone by determining potential markets in advance and transparently highlighting relevant conditions. Market analysis, development of regulatory strategies and on-site visits help you to
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	<p>develop a comprehensive understanding of the opportunities and challenges of the target country. If you are interested in entering the German market, we are also there to assist you. We can provide you with essential information about the German market and the healthcare system and work out the optimal project plan together with you.</p> <p>You don't know where to start? Are you looking for impulses, inspiration, answers or the right questions? If you don't know what you need to bring your startup forward or if you are interested in topics that are not listed here, please, feel free to contact us.</p>
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	https://www.medical-valley-emn.de/en/ourservices/services-for-startups/
Type of activity	Various services for startups in the health sector
Target group	Startups from the health sector
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.medical-valley-emn.de/en/ourservices/services-for-startups/
Application deadline	Application is always possible.
Date and time of the activity	Ongoing activities
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	Yes
2. Name	EXISTENCY Professionalize Program (in cooperation with ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator)
Short description	<p>Once you have founded a company, then the adventure really begins.</p> <p>You do and decide many things for the first time. You also have to do some things differently and think in a new way. In reality, many things are quite different from what you thought. What could be better than learning from those who are already one step ahead of you? To make this possible for you, we have various offers that show you how reasons work in reality.</p> <p>Sometimes, however, when you're setting up your own company, you keep coming up against certain limits, you keep having similar questions, and that's why you need specific support from</p>

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	<p>outside. Or you simply need to look over the shoulders of others who have been doing it all for a while.</p> <p>For such situations we have brought a strong partner on board: the Zollhof - Tech Incubator opens its network exclusively for you. Together, you first analyze the current situation and identify who can best help you - whether it's an experienced start-up, an industry specialist, or a topic expert, Zollhof will bring you together with the right people either on the mentoring track or on the trainee track. (For further information see https://www.existency.de/files/2023/04/EXISTENCY-Professionalize.pdf.)</p> <p>About every 4 weeks it's networking time - the Gründungscafé offers you input from experts, experience reports from other start-ups, exchange with other entrepreneurs and above all many good contacts in our - and thus also in your - network. Learning from each other and with each other, that is the principle of the start-up café.</p>
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	https://www.existency.de/professionalize/
Type of activity	Networking with professionals for startups
Target group	Startups
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	See https://www.existency.de/files/2023/04/EXISTENCY-Professionalize.pdf and https://www.existency.de/professionalize/
Application deadline	Application is always possible.
Date and time of the activity	Ongoing activities
Is it English-speaking?	Yes (partly)
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	No
<i>Key startup support programs and courses on the level of acceleration at ITU</i>	
1. Name	Innogate International Acceleration Program

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Short description	Innogate is an International Acceleration Program that connects Turkish technology companies with potential customers, investors and business partners in the global markets by providing training, consultancy and coaching in order to help them expand into global markets. As a result, it is a program that enables companies to replicate their success in Turkey across the globe through the program.
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Istanbul (& USA or UK)
Type of activity	Acceleration activities (seminars, keynotes, coaching, sales consultancy, investor demo days)
Target group	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology-based companies that have reached mid or large-scale • ‘Born global’ start-ups with high tech
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://innogate.org/en/homepage/
Application deadline	Tbd
Date and time of the activity	Tbd
Is it English-speaking?	Yes
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	This needs to be discussed. Currently the program is a paid program as participant companies are expected to pay fees (however, government subsidies are also present).

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of acceleration at SNS

None

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of acceleration at SSSA

None

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of acceleration at UPB

1. Name	Innovation Labs Demo Day and Long-Term Support
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Short description	The latter stages of Innovation Labs focus on events that gather teams, mentors, and ambassadors, partners of the program as well as different stakeholders from the educational and entrepreneurial ecosystem. The first event is the “Startups Fair”, where teams will be presenting their technical demo and networking with various stakeholders. The second event is the “Demo Day”, where teams hold a 2 minutes’ pitch in front of the audience, showcasing the product built over the past three months, and compete for the jury’s recognition. Finally, Innovation Labs also offers long-term support, helping teams that choose to continue working on their product and still need technical guidance and advice on certain issues, such as scaling their start-up or applying for specialized accelerator programs.
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	Bucharest, Brasov, Sibiu (Romania)
Type of activity	Demos and long-term support
Target group	Students, university research groups, senior teams
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	https://www.innovationlabs.ro/program
Application deadline	February (yearly)
Date and time of the activity	May – July (yearly)
Is it English-speaking?	No
Is it already open to EELISA partners?	It is open to anyone
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Yes, most likely

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of acceleration at BME

None

Key startup support programs and courses on the level of acceleration at PSL

1. Name	PSL Tech Acceleration
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This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811

Short description	<p>The PSL Tech Acceleration program aims to offer enhanced support for deep tech startups within the PSL – Pasteur community, focusing on their access to the market and on human resources.</p> <p>The PSL Tech Acceleration program comprises the Deep Tech Institute for training and the Deep Tech Accelerator for acceleration. Accelerated startups will benefit from support and services aimed at accelerating their incubation towards the market, providing them with high-level support for market analysis, for their partnerships and pre-industrial co-developments, and in strengthening their leadership and teams. PSL Tech Acceleration is coordinated by Université PSL, with the involvement of four of its Component Schools (Chimie Paris - PSL, Dauphine - PSL, ESPCI Paris - PSL, MINES Paris - PSL), Institut Curie (associate member) and Institut Pasteur. It has secured €1.5 million in funding over two years through the Bpifrance "Intégration SIA" call for proposals. It will build on the entrepreneurial dynamics of the ecosystem and create a structured acceleration program, complemented by training for entrepreneurs and researchers.</p> <p>PSL Tech Acceleration has become part of the PSL – Pasteur ecosystem, complementing the support provided to startups by the incubators and by the associated development services.</p> <p>For further information see: https://psl.eu/en/innovation/entrepreneurship-psl/psl-tech-acceleration</p>
Location of the program or course (address, if online: link)	On-site at PSL
Type of activity	Acceleration Program
Target group	Deep tech startups
Registration (Link or contact e-mail address)	For details about the application process see: https://psl.eu/en/innovation/entrepreneurship-psl/psl-tech-acceleration
Application deadline	Ongoing
Date and time of the activity	The duration of the support will be adapted to the needs of the projects, and will typically be from 12 to 18 months.
Is it English-speaking?	Yes

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Is it already open to EELISA partners?	No
Can it be opened to EELISA partners?	Tbd

Table 7: Key startup support programs and courses at all EELISA partner institutions on the level of acceleration (professional startup skills and knowledge)

3.1.7 Summary overview of the EELISA landscape of startup support in two figures

The following two figures provide a summary overview of the EELISA landscape of startup support detailed in the previous sections: Figure 1 provides a summary overview of the “EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part A: Key Startup Support Institutions and Services” and figure 2 provides a summary overview of the “EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part B: Key Startup Support Programs and Courses”. These figures will not only greatly help to get a better overview of the EELISA landscape of startup support, but also be highly useful for the second and third pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan, when it comes to the sharing of our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses as well as to the implementation of an EELISA-wide startup initiative that (strategically) builds on and supplements the existing EELISA landscape of startup support.

EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part A: Key Startup Support Institutions and Services

NUCLEATION	INCUBATION	ACCELERATION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UPM CAIT (UPM) • FAU Startup Service (FAU) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actúaupm Network of Investors and Experts (UPM) • ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU) • JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab (FAU) • Medical Valley (FAU) • ITU Cekirdek (ITU) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator (FAU) • JOSEPHS – The Open Innovation Lab (FAU) • Medical Valley (FAU) • JoTTO (SSSA) • Third Mission Administrative Area (SSSA)
OPEN TO EELISA		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurship Group UPM (UPM) • UPM Partnership with Banco Santander (UPM) • Makerspace (ENPC) • Fablab Descartes (ENPC) • FAU Digital Tech Academy (FAU) • ITU GINOVA (ITU) • Knowledge Transfer Office (SNS) • JoTTO Office (SNS) • Contamination Lab (SNS) • Start Cup Toscana 2023 (SSSA) • UPBiz Entrepreneurship Center (UPB) • BME US(3) (BME) • Technology Transfer Services at PSL (PSL) • Mines Paris – PSL coworking space (PSL) • PSL-Lab (PSL coworking space) (PSL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage 4 actúaupm (UPM) • Entrepreneurship Group UPM (UPM) • UPM Partnership with Banco Santander (UPM) • Incubateur Descartes (ENPC) • d.school Paris (ENPC) • Station F (ENPC) • Co-Innovation Lab ENPC (ENPC) • NKubator (FAU) • LZE (FAU) • EXISTENCY (FAU) • Agreement and collaboration with POLO TECNOLOGICO NAVACCHIO (SNS) • JUMP (SSSA) • Innovation Labs (UPB) • BME US(3) (BME) • Incubateur Paris-Dauphine (PSL) • PC Up (PSL) • Chimie Paris Innov (PSL) • PSL Tech Seed (PSL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspiring women (UPM) • EXISTENCY (UPM) • ITU ARI teknoent (ITU) • Innovation Labs (UPB) • PSL Innovation Fund (PSL)
NOT OPEN TO EELISA OR NOT ENGLISH-SPEAKING		

Figure 1: EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part A: Key Startup Support Institutions and Services

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EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part B: Key Startup Support Programs and Courses

NUCLEATION	INCUBATION	ACCELERATION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> actuaupm (UPM) Introduction to Intra/Social Entrepreneurship (UPM) Starting Business Ideas @FAU (FAU) Technology transfer in nanotechnologies: IP protection, spin-offs (SNS) High Tech Entrepreneurship Course (SSSA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Medical Valley Services for Startups (FAU) ITU SEED Acceleration Program (ITU) BME US(3) (BME) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Medical Valley Services for Startups (FAU)
OPEN TO EELISA		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FAU Digital Tech Fellows Program (FAU) Impact(3) (FAU) Entrepreneurship Bootcamp (from UPBizz) (UPB) Grand Challenges Scholars Program (from UPBizz) (UPB) BME's Business Express Program (BME) The PSL-Pépîte entrepreneurship training program (PSL) PSL-Teams (entrepreneurship awareness program) (PSL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stage 4 training (UPM) UPM TT Course (UPM) d.school Paris: Programme ME310 (ENPC) ZOLLHOF Talent Program (FAU) ZOLLHOF Startup Incubation Program (FAU) EXISTENCY Reality Bites (FAU) Innovation Labs Hackathon and Pre-Acceleration Phases (UPB) Incubation Programs at the Incubator Paris-Dauphine (PSL) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EXISTENCY Professionalize Program (in cooperation with ZOLLHOF Tech Incubator) (FAU) Innagate International Acceleration Program (ITU) Innovation Labs Demo Day and Long-Term Support (UPB) PSL Tech Acceleration (PSL)
NOT OPEN TO EELISA OR NOT ENGLISH-SPEAKING		

Figure 2: EELISA Landscape of Startup Support Part B: Key Startup Support Programs and Courses

3.2 The second pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan: The sharing of key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses

Having developed the EELISA landscape of startup support on all three levels of the startup journey, now the question arises, how we can share this landscape among all EELISA partners so that we can create new opportunities for our startups and founders. In the following, we will give an answer to this question with the second pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan that outlines the ways of sharing our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses on all levels of the startup journey. We will proceed in seven steps of which the first two steps have already been taken:

Firstly, with the EELISA landscape of startup support, developed in the first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan, we have already created an overview of our key startup support resources that will serve as a knowledge base for sharing these resources. In fact, putting these key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses on the map of the EELISA landscape of startup support is already a first way of sharing them at least potentially. In such a way the EELISA landscape of startup support will serve as a basis for future discussions about actually sharing our key startup support resources. As this knowledge base is indispensable, we will keep the EELISA landscape of startup support updated and use it as a basis for future discussions about sharing and further developing it. The updates can be achieved by creating a shared living document on the basis of the current state of the

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EELISA landscape of startup support developed in this deliverable that is to be regularly kept up to date by all partner institutions. Thus, all EELISA partners can easily get a complete and up-to-date overview of our EELISA landscape of startup support that will serve as a basis for future discussions about meaningfully sharing and further developing our key startup support resources.

Secondly, as can be seen from the EELISA landscape of startup support, developed in the first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan, we have also already shared the first key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses with all EELISA partner institutions. This already offers several new opportunities to our startups and founders. From the EELISA landscape of startup support, we can see which institutions, services, programs, and courses are already open to EELISA and which ones are not, but might nevertheless be of interest for future activities.

The third step of sharing our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses will be to interlink them as meaningfully as possible. The aim of this step is twofold: On the one hand, we will try to reallocate resources strategically (in the long run). This will allow us to avoid duplicate structures wherever possible, to use our resources where they are needed the most, and to further strengthen our existing capacities. For example, if a certain EELISA partner institution has no online course to provide basic startup skills and knowledge on the level of nucleation and one or several other EELISA partner institutions do have such courses that are open to EELISA, then there might be no need to use additional resources to establish yet another course. Moreover, the resources saved could be used either for more urgent activities for which no or not enough offers do exist yet or for further improving existing offers. On the other hand, interlinking our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses will allow our institutions to learn from each other, to exchange best practices, and to benefit from complementary strengths and resources.

The fourth step of sharing our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses will consist in promoting our offers purposefully. Thus, we can improve our resource utilization and increase the outreach of our institutions, services, programs, and courses. The main means of promoting our entrepreneurship activities will be the EELISA media channels for innovation and the EELISA community platform. Targeted promotion of our activities is key to successfully reach the potential and actual startups and founders for whom the activities are offered.

Fifthly, another useful way of sharing our key startup support resources might be to transform the mapping of the EELISA landscape of startup support or at least those elements that are open to EELISA into an overview on the EELISA website. This would make our startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses more visible and better accessible. Furthermore, it would also help to make our resources better coordinated. When setting up new activities, our startup support institutions and services could use the overview on the EELISA website to fill the gaps by planning missing activities and to offer them at suitable times without overlaps.

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The aim would be to have attractive offers on all levels of the startup journey and to make them visible and accessible to our potential and actual startups and founders.

Sixthly, we will continue our discussions about connecting and sharing our key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses by joint events and small thematic meetings. In this context, it would be helpful to integrate all of the experts and CEOs from these institutions and services directly or indirectly into the discussions. This would allow not only to learn from each other, but also to systematically interconnect our resources and to develop additional offers for our potential and actual startups and founders. This might also include on-site visits and workshops.

Seventhly, we not only want to open and share the existing offers of startup support among all members of our EELISA European University, but also to fill the gaps and to create new joint offers. This will be done by WP7 and with the activities proposed in the third pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan.

3.3 The third pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan: The implementation of an EELISA-wide startup initiative

The third pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan outlines the implementation of an EELISA-wide startup initiative that will take place in the third year of the EELISA InnoCORE project between June 2023 and May 2024. Our aim with this initiative is not only to open as many of the existing key startup support institutions, services, programs, and courses listed in the first pillar of the EELISA entrepreneurship action plan by the means proposed in the second pillar, but also to fill the gaps in the EELISA landscape of startup support by organizing additional joint events for our startups and founders that create new opportunities and added value for them. Most importantly, our goal is to raise the probability of successful market entry of our startups in all our partner cities and eventually across the entire EELISA innovation ecosystem. This is particularly relevant as EELISA European University covers lucrative markets for startups in Southern Europe (Italy and Spain), Western Europe (France and Germany), Eastern Europe (Hungary and Romania), as well as in Turkey as the gateway between Europe and Asia. By opening our innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems for startups from EELISA partners we want to offer our startups the additional opportunities that such a European ecosystem can offer. We will primarily aim at existing startups at the verge of market entry. For them, we will organize various activities that will provide them with new skills, knowledge, and access to networks from which they will benefit in their startup journey. These activities may be boot camps, workshops, mentoring programs, demo days, and startup contests. What is important is that these activities will give our startups access to an advanced EELISA landscape of startup support where they will:

- profit from the startup support expertise and resources that can be provided by EELISA European University,
- get access to EELISA partners' innovation and entrepreneurship ecosystems beyond their home institutions,

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- get informed about how investors actually work in different national markets,
- become familiar with general basics like “product market fit”, “investor readiness”, “pitching” or “negotiation”,
- learn about the methods of design thinking,
- have the possibility to learn from each other and from more advanced startups,
- get the opportunity to collaborate on a European level and to build an international network already at an early stage,
- get international feedback and the opportunity to further improve their business plans,
- and have the possibility and support (in the ideal case also the financial support of investors) to scale on a European level.

We will offer several of these activities in the roll out phase of this EELISA entrepreneurship action plan between June 2023 and May 2024. The highlight of our activities will be the second edition of the EELISA startup contest that will be hosted by FAU towards the end of the project. We plan to invite the winners of startup demo days or selected startups from each EELISA partner institution to FAU to participate in mentoring, to network, and to pitch in front of an international jury composed of members from all EELISA partners and possibly also in front of invited investors. This event will help our startups become more professional and successful in domestic and possibly international markets.

By implementing this EELISA-wide startup initiative we will leverage the expertise and resources of EELISA European University to help our startups and founders transform their ideas into successful businesses that will contribute to the creation of a desirable future. At the end of the project, we will evaluate the success of our joint entrepreneurial activities in another deliverable (D7.4). By then, we will hopefully have successfully established an advanced EELISA landscape of startup support with many valuable offers for nascent entrepreneurs as well as existing startups and founders.

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